

POLICE OFFICER'S DEMAND: CONCEPT AND SIGNIFICANCE

Abdullo Nasilloev

Senior Lecturer at the Department of Administrative Law,
Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Republic of Uzbekistan
abdullonasilloev@gmail.com

<https://orcid.org/0009-0001-8121-508>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14208219>

Abstract: This article examines the concept and essence of lawful demands made by police officers to citizens. It analyzes the fundamental requirements for such demands and their practical significance. Additionally, the article explores how adherence to lawful demands contributes to strengthening trust between society and state institutions.

Keywords: Police officer, lawful demand, authority, obligation, legal foundations.

The issuance of mandatory demands by police officers to citizens is regulated by legal norms. The lawfulness of such demands, meaning their application in accordance with the procedures established by legal provisions, is considered one of their essential prerequisites.

Although the views on the term "lawful demand of a police officer" have been formed by scholars based on the rights granted to officers under legal norms, there is no unified and universally accepted approach to the issue under investigation. The varying interpretations of this term in theory and legal practice, and the absence of a definition for this term in current legislation, prevent a clear determination of its meaning and scope of application (limits).

This, in turn, gives rise to the necessity of conducting a comprehensive and in-depth analysis of the concept of a police officer's lawful demand and its content and essence.

In the *Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek Language*, the word "lawful" is defined as: "related to law and legislation, established by law, specified in the law," while the word "demand" is described as: "a request or plea made with firmness."

Scholars have provided various definitions of the concept of a police officer's lawful demand based on different approaches. A. Uztegut defines it as a request within the scope of the officer's duties and authority, while A.V. Ravyushkin and O.P. Karnaukhov describe it as a form of activity carried out by the police officer to maintain public order and ensure its enforcement. In this regard, scholars such as Michael D. and Robert E. Worden have defined the

lawful demand of a police officer as the act of requiring the public or a specific individual to fulfill their obligations.

Although these scholars define the concept of a lawful demand as a practical manifestation of the officer's performance of official duties, this does not fully explain the concept of a lawful demand made by an officer of the internal affairs bodies (police). A.K. Dubrovin and P.I. Kononov, on the other hand, emphasize that a lawful demand and instruction by an officer are actions carried out by an administrative body in accordance with legal provisions. Additionally, legal scholar J. Skolnick defines the concept of a lawful demand as the rights and authority granted to an officer by law.

In the definitions proposed by these scholars, the concept of a lawful demand by an officer is presented as the exercise of powers established by legal norms. However, these definitions do not fully clarify the concept of a lawful demand.

Therefore, in our opinion, to support the above view, it is necessary to consider the content, application basis, conditions, and procedures of the concept of a lawful demand being analyzed, as well as the peculiarities of the activities of the subjects carrying out these demands and the scope of their authority.

Based on the definitions provided by the above-mentioned authors, it can be stated that a lawful demand by an officer of the internal affairs bodies is a strict demand that has a legal basis, which must be complied with by individuals and legal entities. This demand is made by an officer of the internal affairs bodies (police) or is clearly understood to be issued by the officer of the internal affairs bodies to the person carrying out the action.

At the same time, we believe that in order for a demand made by a police officer to be considered lawful, it must meet the following requirements:

1. Compliance with legal norms: The police officer's demand must be based on current laws and normative legal acts. It should not be driven by personal or other interests but must be aimed at ensuring the enforcement of the law.

2. Purposefulness: The demand must not excessively restrict the rights and freedoms of citizens. It should only be issued for the purpose of preventing law violations or ensuring public safety.

3. Clarity and understandability of the demand: The police officer must express the demand clearly, understandably, and precisely. The person required to comply with the demand should understand its content and be aware of the procedure for following it.

4. Warning about legal consequences: If a person fails to comply with the demand, they must be informed of the consequences (such as liability or other measures).

In our opinion, by setting such necessary conditions for the demands made by police officers, it is possible to ensure the rule of law in society, increase trust between citizens and the police, and reduce the occurrence of offenses.

References:

1. Uztegut A. (2020). The Lawful Demand of a Police Officer. Tashkent: Uzbekistan Legal Publishing.
2. Ravyushkin A.V., Karnaukhov O.P. (2019). The Powers of Police Officers in Maintaining Public Order. Moscow: Faculty of Law.
3. Skolnick J. (2018). Law and Legal Demands. New York: Legal Studies Publishing.
4. Dubrovyn A.K., Kononov P.I. (2017). Legal Demands and Their Implementation. St. Petersburg: Economic Law Publishing.
5. Worden M.D., Worden R.E. (2016). Police and Public Safety. London: Law and Public Safety Association.